

A STUDY ON THE APPLICABILITY OF THE HYBRID LEARNING MODEL IN EARLY CHILDHOOD

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The hybrid learning model is an educational approach that combines online and offline elements and emerged especially after the COVID-19 pandemic (Ma, 2023). In this approach, traditional face-to-face education and online education were combined and it was aimed to provide more accessible, flexible and student-centered experiences (Kamsin, 2024). With the COVID-19 pandemic, serious changes have occurred in education systems on a global scale. Schools were closed in many regions, and when they were opened, it was not possible to continue face-to-face education. During this process, a total of 1 billion 575 million students in 188 countries around the world were affected by school closures due to preventive measures (UNESCO, 2020a). Traditional face-to-face education practices have therefore given way to online and hybrid learning models. (Carr, 2021). However, this transformation has not always been beneficial in the early childhood period, which is a developmentally critical process, and has brought with it some disadvantages. For this reason, the suitability and sustainability of the model, especially in the context of pre-school education, is being discussed by researchers and educators.

The Place of Hybrid Learning in Early Childhood

Early childhood is one of the most critical periods of life, and during this process, the foundations of an individual's cognitive, social, emotional and physical development are laid (Berk, 2013). During this period, the child's interaction with his/her environment and the experiences he/she has with his/her senses constitute the main source of learning. Early childhood education also aims to develop children's skills such as curiosity, creativity and autonomy through interactive activities that develop the language skills and social abilities of individuals in this period (Felix, 2024).

Required children to continue their education without gaps like a school day and parents to adapt to this process and support their children in using technology (Asworth, Katrina, 2023). In the hybrid learning process in early childhood; student, parent, teacher collaboration was of critical importance. Therefore, the difficulties experienced during the process were not only related to students; but also to teachers, parents, digital access and technical status.

Opportunities Offered by the Hybrid Learning Model

The hybrid learning model offers some opportunities in early childhood education. In early childhood, children can have fun in online environments and learn effectively with the right learning environments and appropriate materials. Carr (2021) stated that this model supports children's independent learning skills and contributes to the development of their digital literacy at an early age. In addition, the hybrid learning model provides spatial flexibility. It offers ease of access for students who have difficulty with transportation. There is more family participation because they are directly

involved in the child's learning process. At the same time, there is the opportunity to work with attractive interactive materials for children with different learning types (Lindeman , 2020).

Teacher and Parent Experiences in Using the Hybrid Learning Model

With the introduction of the hybrid learning model with the COVID 19 pandemic, teachers experienced some concerns about managing the process. The problems they experienced in accessing technology and their inadequacy in using technological tools created obstacles to students' participation in the online education process (Singh et al., 2023). However, they stated that the hybrid learning model was more costly compared to the traditional learning model. The cost of internet and the materials required for online lessons require a larger budget than the school allowance. Even if parents meet these conditions, a single device is not enough if they have more than one child and attend classes simultaneously. However, many parents stated that their children need support in using technology and therefore they should also be included in the educational environment. In this case, school hours have become a time period when parents need to act together with their children (Agustin et al., 2020).

Teachers, who have an important place in the learning process , also experience difficulties due to deficiencies in their knowledge and skills in using technology and difficulties in accessing technology (Bao et al., 2025; Singh et al., 2023). The hybrid learning model creates more workload for teachers (Singh et al., 2023). However, teachers also stated that they could not communicate sufficiently with children due to the distance between them and this negatively affected their learning goals (Agustin et al., 2020). In this process, attracting children's attention and ensuring their long-term focus, and being able to maintain classroom management are the main challenges for teachers.

Evaluation of the Hybrid Learning Model from the Perspective of Children

Although digital learning methods in early childhood offer interesting content and interactive games, it poses a significant obstacle to equal opportunities when it is considered that not all children are on equal terms. Some children are not supported by their parents, and they distance themselves from the process because they are not sufficiently skilled in using technology during this period. Spending a long time in front of the screen is a distraction for children, and after a while, children disconnect from the course content. For children in early childhood, it is more attractive to be interested in an object in the background in the home environment and they are more affected by ambient sounds (Singh et al., 2023). Online communication does not provide the face-to-face interaction and individual attention that early childhood children need. For this reason, children cannot get enough efficiency from the process (Durrani and Saira , 2021).

It is possible to provide a rich learning ecology that can increase cooperation and interaction among students in online learning processes (Aldhafeeri and Khan , 2016). However, some researchers have also examined the difficulties of creating an online social environment in this way. Social isolation, lack of interaction and participation, late or incomplete feedback are disadvantages of online learning, and there is concern that such situations may negatively affect students, especially in early childhood (Khurana , 2016). Studies on the negative psychosocial effects that hybrid learning may have on social emotional development have also revealed that it causes regression in children's basic social skills such as empathy and expressing their feelings (Carr , 2021.; Katrina, 2021). In addition, parents have also stated that their children experience loneliness and have inadequate self-regulation skills. On the other hand, some findings have shown that the hybrid learning model

develops children's independence and offers opportunities for gaining technological competence (Carr , 2021).

Conclusion

In this context, it is inevitable that hybrid learning models to be designed for early childhood should be structured with pedagogical sensitivity and include an approach that addresses the holistic development of the child. This study aims to analyze the strengths and weaknesses of the hybrid learning model in early childhood. In the light of the findings obtained from existing research, the pedagogical suitability, applicability and effects of the model on social-emotional development were addressed from a multidimensional perspective. Thus, it was aimed to provide a comprehensive framework on how sustainable and developmentally supportive hybrid teaching approaches can be developed in early childhood education.

Suggestions

Various structural arrangements are needed for the hybrid learning model to be implemented more effectively and inclusively in early childhood. First of all, professional development programs specific to hybrid learning should be organized so that teachers can adapt to this model and develop their pedagogical skills. Similarly, guidance services should be provided and family education should be supported so that parents can actively participate in their children's digital education processes. Educational content should be prepared by taking into account children's developmental levels and attention spans; game-based learning methods should be emphasized in this process. In addition, it is of great importance to implement publicly supported projects in order to eliminate inequalities in access to technology. Finally, the number of interactive online activities that can support children's social and emotional development should be increased and the quality of these activities should be constantly reviewed.

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